

D-JRP23-WP4.1 - Sequence inventory report

WP3

Responsible Partner: SSI

Contributing partners: AGES, ANSES, APHA, INIAV, INSA, IP, ISS, IZLER, PHE, Pivet, RIVM, Sciensano, VISAVET and WBVR

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SEQUENCE INVENTORY REPORT

Salmonella Enteritidis sequence inventory

1. Adonis project

Salmonellosis remains the second most common zoonosis in humans in the EU despite a significantly long-term decreasing trend in human cases since 2008. In recent years this decreasing trend has levelled off. In laying hens, the prevalence of positive flocks for the target serovars, and especially for *S. Enteritidis*, has also increased after a long period of documented reduction. Several hypotheses have been made, including more complete reporting and improvements in the surveillance of human salmonellosis, premature relaxation of *Salmonella* control measures at primary production, possible deficiencies in the enforcement of existing control measures and sensitivity of statutory sampling programmes, and changed/increased exposure patterns.

The ADONIS project will identify determinants underlying the stagnation/reversal of the decreasing trend in *Salmonella* Enteritidis incidence in humans and poultry in the EU. We will apply a cross-sectorial approach in which we investigate possible explanatory factors at the levels of primary production, epidemiology/exposure, and the pathogen itself. This will all be done over the period that spans the observed turning stagnation point.

At the primary production level, the project will evaluate possible changes in flock management and possible insufficiencies in control measures implemented to date in poultry farms related to the implementation of vaccination programmes as well as the application of strict farm hygiene controls and sensitivity of the statutory sampling implemented in commercial flocks.

At the public health level, this project will evaluate national surveillance systems for *S. Enteritidis* in humans, assess changes over time regarding epidemiological characteristics, and calculate the total reservoir output exposure loads.

At the pathogen level, we will assess whether the recent plateau in salmonellosis incidence in Europe could be related to the genetic variation of the *Salmonella* bacterium, primarily *S. Enteritidis*, such as the emergence or clonal expansion of specific bacterial strains with increased fitness in the form of e.g. increased bacterial division, increased virulence or antibiotic resistance.

Finally, the data and information gathered will be ranked and prioritized by a Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) modelling.

The pathogen level is investigated in WP4 and we will investigate whether the recent plateau in salmonellosis incidence in Europe could be related to the genetic variation of the *Salmonella* bacterium, primarily *S. Enteritidis*, such as the emergence or clonal expansion of specific bacterial strains with increased fitness in the form of e.g. increased bacterial division, increased virulence or antibiotic resistance. For this purpose we will create a collection of genomes from strains sampled from humans and foods and strains sampled in primary production with special attention to laying hens and broilers. We will focus on sampling broadly in the years 2008-2012 and 2013-2019 to cover the time before and after incidence change.

Initially, we will provide a general overview of the population structure of *S. Enteritidis* through WGS by investigating evolutionary micro-events in the core genome (i.e. SNPs and InDels) and evolutionary macro-events in the accessory genome (gene gains and losses). The accessory genome will be analysed by comparative genomics regarding presence of virulence genes, (pro)phages, plasmids, replicons and AMR profiles in isolates from the different time periods. In addition, we will elucidate the long and short term evolution and emergence of different clones over time and their most recent common ancestor (MRCA). We will also assess the potential increase of successful clones in the bacterial effective population size. Finally, we will investigate whether differences in phenotype exist

between isolates gathered over time and whether there are there any genomic differences that can be related to these phenotypes (Genome Wide Association Studies). We will gain knowledge and actionable information on the evolutionary potential of these clones and the biological functions involved.

The work will embrace 4 tasks: i) an overview of WGS data available at all partners and in public repositories, ii) population structure and comparative genomics, iii) phylodynamics and phylogeography, and iv) mutant creation and GWAS to identify the possible genetic elements responsible for phenotype changes.

The collection of *Salmonella* Enteritidis strains that has been created for this project is undergoing sequencing at the individual partner institutes and the entire collection of strains that will be sequenced is presented in this report.

Figure1. The countries that participate in the project coloured by the source of strains that are supplied by the individual partners. Categories are divided into strains originating from (1) animal, food and feed, (2) humans or (3) both.

1.1. Sequence collection of isolates from Animal, Food and Feed

Each partner was limited to supply 5 sequences per year (2008-2019) pr category (Breeders, Broilers and Laying hens). The resulting collection is displayed in **figure 2**. The strains should be selected with the aim of representing as many farms and production facilities as possible to gain widest possible diversity. Additionally, the intitutes were able to include approximately 10 % extra isolates from other sources of animal or environmental origin.

Figure2. The total number of strains from the different years divided into the different categories of animals.

Furthermore, each partner was limited to supply 5 sequences per year (2008-2019) per category of Food (Chicken meat and Eggs) and Feed. The resulting collection is displayed in figure 3.

Figure3. The total number of strains from the different years divided into the different categories of Food (Eggs and chicken meat) and Feed.

Additional strains selected for sequencing originate from other animals such as Turkey, Calves, Pigs and different wild animals. Also strains from different foods such as spices, shellfish, seeds and other has been collected. All will be included in the collection.

Animal, Food and Feed data from the UK are not included in figures 2 and 3.

1.2. Sequence collection of isolates from Humans

Each partner was limited to supply 5 randomly selected sequences per year (2008-2019) of human origin, preferably isolated from patients with no travel history. We also checked for outbreak cases, making sure only a single case from an outbreak was included in the collection. The collection is shown in **figure 4**. Additionally the different institutions were able to include approximately 10 % extra isolates from historic collections (isolated before 2008).

Figure4. The total number of strains from the different years.

Roughly 100 sequences from strains primarily isolated in the 1980's, 1990's and 2000's were included from Denmark, Portugal and the Netherlands.